

Synthesis of 2-Aryl-3-[5'-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl]-5-*H*/methyl-4-thiazolidinones as Antimicrobial Agents

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In view of biological activities of 4-thiazolidinones and 1,3,4-thiadiazoles¹, the title compounds have been synthesised with a presumption that these would reveal biological activities.

2-Hydroxyphenyl-3-thiosemicarbazide was prepared by the reaction of 2-hydroxybenzoyl hydrazine and ammonium thiocyanate. These on acidic cyclisation furnished 2-amino-5-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole² (1). Compound 1 on treatment with arylaldehydes yielded 2 followed by the action of thioglycolic or thiolactic acid to afford 3 and 4.

2-4a-h

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|---|--|
| a, R = C ₆ H ₅ | h, R = C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH |
| b, R = 3-OH C ₆ H ₄ | i, R = 2-Cl C ₆ H ₄ |
| c, R = 4-OH C ₆ H ₄ | j, R = 3-Cl C ₆ H ₄ |
| d, R = 5-OH 3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₃ | k, R = 4-Cl C ₆ H ₄ |
| e, R = 5-Br 4-OH 3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₂ | l, R = 2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ |
| f, R = 5-Br 2-OH C ₆ H ₃ | m, R = 3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ |
| g, R = 3,5-(Br) ₂ 2-OH C ₆ H ₂ | n, R = 4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ |

Compounds 2-4 were screened for their biological activity³ against bacteria *S. aureus*, *E. coli* and fungi *A. niger*,

C. albicans at a concentration of 50 μg ml⁻¹ in DMF using standard drugs ampicillin, chloramphenicol, norfloxacin and griseofulvin. Compounds 2i, k, m and n showed antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* comparable to ampicillin and norfloxacin. Compounds 2d, e, n, j-n, w-y showed antifungal activity against *A. niger* comparable to griseofulvin.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) was recorded on a Shimadzu 435 spectrophotometer and pmr on a Hitachi R 1200 (60 MHz) (DMSO-d₆ + CDCl₃) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

2-Benzalamino-5-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (2a): A mixture of benzaldehyde (1.06 g, 0.01 mol) and 2-amino-5-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (1.93 g, 0.01 mol) in methanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The contents were then poured into ice-water and the resulting solid was washed with sodium bisulphite solution then with water and crystallised from methanol-dioxane-water (3 : 2 : 0.5), (74%), m.p. 150°; ν_{max} 3 400-3 300 (OH), 1 665 (C=N exocyclic), 1 610 (C=N cyclic), 1 590 (N=CH), 1 445, 1 310, 1 170 (1,3,4-thiadiazolic ring), 690 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); δ 7.68 (1H, s, N=CH), 6.52-7.1 (9H, m, ArH), 11.7 (1H, s, OH).

Similarly, other aromatic aldehydes were prepared (yields 60-92%): 2b, m.p. 180°; c, 112°; d, 90°; e, 155°; f, 160°; g, 173°; h, 110°; i, 120°; j, 95°; k, 80°; l, 80°; m, 101°, n, 138°.

2-Phenyl-3-(5'-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl)-5-*H*/methyl-4-thiazolidinones (3a, 4a): A mixture of 2-benzalamino-5-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (0.965 g, 0.005 mol) and thioglycolic acid (0.005 mol)/thiolactic acid (0.005 mol) in benzene (50 ml) in the presence of anhydrous ZnCl₂ (0.5 g) and refluxed at 160° for 2 h. The temperature was then raised to 180° and maintained for 0.5 h. Excess of benzene was distilled off and the content poured into ice-water, and the resulting solid was washed with dilute solution of sodium bicarbonate and water and crystallised from ethanol: 3a (52%), m.p. 180°; ν_{max} 3 400-3 300 (OH), 1 695 (C=O), 1 440, 1 320, 1 180 (1,3,4-thiadiazolic ring), 710 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); δ 6.68-7.18 (9H, m, ArH and S-CH-Ar), 3.88 (2H, s, SCH₂CO), 11.65 (1H, s, OH), 13.8 (1H, s, OH enolic of 4-thiazolidinones); 4a (68%), m.p. 120°; ν_{max} 3 400-3 300 (OH), 1 700

(C=O), 1 450, 1 330, 1 175 (1,3,4-thiadiazolic ring), 710 cm^{-1} (C-S-C); δ 1.4 (3H, d, CHCH_3), 3.6 (1H, q, CHCH_3), 3.66 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.21 (1H, s, N=CH), 6.65-7.21 (9H, m, ArH), 11.69 (1H, s, OH), 13.79 (1H, s, OH enolic of 4-thiazolidinone). Similarly, other compounds were synthesised (yields 52-86%): **3b**, m.p. 200°; **c**, 120°; **d**, 160°; **e**, 175°; **f**, 250°; **g**, 230°; **h**, 190°; **i**, 180°; **j**, 75°; **k**, 101°; **l**, 150°; **m**, 79°; **n**, 100°; **4b**, m.p. 210°; **c**, 179°; **d**, 220°; **e**, 125°; **f**, 179°; **g**, 210°; **h**, 135°; **i**, 105°; **j**, 120°; **k**, 179°; **l**, 125°; **m**, 85°; **n**, 110°.

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